

2025

InnerSource Commons

State of InnerSource Report

Foreword

I am thrilled to see the State of InnerSource 2025 report come to fruition. This work represents an invaluable contribution to our understanding of how organizations are evolving their collaborative practices.

The findings reveal encouraging progress: organizations increasingly recognize InnerSource as essential infrastructure for breaking down silos and building competitive advantage. As development accelerates and complexity grows, organizational strength lies not just in code, but in accumulated practices, documented decisions, and collaborative culture. InnerSource provides the framework to preserve and share these advantages across the enterprise rather than leaving them fragmented.

Now, we face a new inflection point. AI agents are joining our teams not as distant tools, but as collaborators in daily work. This transformation demands organizations structured for transparent human-AI collaboration. InnerSource principles prove remarkably prescient here. The very practices we've championed (transparency, documented history, open participation) become essential infrastructure for AI-native development.

My deepest gratitude to Clare Dillon and all contributors who made this survey possible. Use these insights to shape your organization's path forward.

Yuki Hattori
President, InnerSource Commons Foundation

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Key Takeaways

1. InnerSource Principles & Practices: InnerSource continues to be defined more by shared values than rigid rules, with collaboration, openness, and transparency ranked as the most important principles.

2. Organizational Motivation and Progress: Organizations are primarily motivated by code reuse, development speed, and breaking down silos. Reported areas of measurable progress closely align, though methods of measurement are still immature.

3. Individual Benefits: At the individual level, InnerSource delivers strong relational and learning benefits. Building relationships and sharing knowledge remain the top perceived benefits, highlighting key areas of value that are often underrepresented in organizational metrics.

4. InnerSource Blockers: Lack of time and resources is the most significant blocker to InnerSource, followed by siloed organizational culture and insufficient management support. These findings reinforce that InnerSource challenges are less technical and more structural and cultural in nature.

5. InnerSource Projects: Libraries and internal tools remain the most common InnerSource project types, with documentation as code continuing to serve as a low-barrier entry point.

6. InnerSource Maturity and Trajectory: Most organizations report being beyond early exploration, with InnerSource practices emerging, growing, or established. Momentum remains broadly positive.

7. InnerSource Tooling and Resources: Foundational tooling such as shared code repositories and documentation is widely available, but more advanced enablement including discovery portals, training, metrics, and automation is uneven. This points to a gap between basic adoption and operational maturity.

8. InnerSource Programs and Resourcing: There is a continued increase in both formal and informal InnerSource programs and ISPOs, indicating growing institutionalization of InnerSource.

9. Emergent Trends: InnerSource and GenAI: For the first time, the survey highlights the growing intersection between InnerSource and GenAI. Organizations are actively exploring multiple entry points, including sharing prompts and knowledge through InnerSource practices, building AI enabled tools collaboratively, integrating AI generated code into InnerSource workflows, and using AI to automate InnerSource tasks such as documentation and code review.

InnerSource Principles and Practices

Defining InnerSource

We asked respondents to define InnerSource in their own words. A small sample of the free-text responses is included below. The fact that no two responses were identical demonstrates that there is no single, fixed definition of InnerSource. While most respondents anchored their definition in applying open source principles and practices inside an organization, the emphasis varies across culture, collaboration, reuse, transparency, and community building.

- *“The idea of applying open source best practices within a company.”*
- *“InnerSource is the use of open source principles and practices to create proprietary software.”*
- *“Applying collaboration practices of opensource within an organization”*
- *“Open Source in closed environments”*
- *“Developing a culture of open source practices within an organization, sharing code across departments, but not necessarily with the world.”*
- *“InnerSource is the practice of applying methodologies and culture, observed in successful open source projects and communities, inside one's organization.”*
- *“A framework for cross-team contributions to software projects within an organisation”*
- *“A software development approach where teams inside the company apply open-source principles and practices to build internal software collaboratively on a shared code base.”*

This diversity reflects InnerSource as a living practice that adapts to organizational context and maturity. However, it also points to an opportunity for InnerSource Commons to help the community move towards a more consistent definition of InnerSource.

What’s important for InnerSource?

InnerSource is not a fixed methodology but an evolving practice that adapts to organizational context, culture, and maturity. Flexibility in adoption trends reflects how InnerSource implementations emphasize what creates value for individual organizations, while still aligning to shared principles. The 2025 State of InnerSource Survey results reflect this clearly.

Respondents prioritized collaboration, openness, and transparency as core InnerSource principles, signaling that InnerSource is first and foremost about changing how people work together across boundaries. Lower emphasis on formal meritocracy or unrestricted freedom to modify indicates a pragmatic adaptation of open source ideas to enterprise realities.

On the practice side, consistent processes and tooling feature high on what is deemed to be most important (e.g. clear contribution guidelines, open tooling, and explicit governance). This suggests that concrete scaffolding and best practices are what make InnerSource workable at scale.

Which of the following principles do you believe are most important for InnerSource? [Max of 3]

n=68

Which of the following practices do you believe are most important for InnerSource? [Max of 5]

n=68

Perceived InnerSource Benefits - Individuals

As with previous years, individuals report benefits of InnerSource that often are not high on the list of organizational motivations. The top two ways respondents perceived InnerSource helping them and their teams included Building Relationships (80%) and Sharing Knowledge (78%). Other reported benefits included Influencing and Communication Skills (77%) and Increased Enjoyment in Work (66%). Additional perceived benefits that also appeared in Organizational Motivations included Code Re-use (69%) and Improved Software Quality (57%). However, for those communicating the benefits of InnerSource, it is worth noting that perceived value may differ depending on whether you are using the individual or organizational lens.

Practicing InnerSource has helped me and my team...

n=60

Perceived InnerSource Blockers

This Lack of Resources / Time Pressure came out on top of perceived blockers to InnerSource (84%). This is consistent with other research and anecdotal evidence from InnerSource Commons, and is a particular issue with new InnerSource initiatives where there may be upfront time and effort required before experiencing the benefits of InnerSource. As in previous years Organizational Culture (silo thinking) also featured highly on the list (74%) and though not as strongly Lack of Overall Awareness was a perceived blocker in 70% of cases.

Lack of executive and middle manager support was called out in 67% and 66% of the cases, respectively. Other perceived blockers included process-related issues including Discoverability (65%) and Lack of Documentation (61%).

To what extent do you agree that each of the following is a significant blocker to InnerSource?

n=59

InnerSource Projects & Practices

InnerSource Projects

Libraries and internal tools (commonly used artifacts) topped the list of InnerSource projects (77%). “Documents as code” was the next most common project type, with 51% of respondents saying that could describe their InnerSource projects. This fits with anecdotal feedback we have heard in InnerSource Commons community calls, suggesting that documentation-as-code is emerging as a common early project type for many organizations.

Platform projects and DevOps projects featured in 47% and 42% of cases respectively, with grassroots or community projects listed by 46% of respondents. Other options included projects where collaboration was pre-planned between development teams (e.g. inter-divisional projects, cross-regional projects) or even organizations (e.g. inter-organization projects or those that span legal boundaries).

32% of respondents declared that InnerSource projects in their organization were on a path to open source in the future. Only 11% of respondents suggested that InnerSource was practiced by default on all projects in their organization.

Describe InnerSource projects in your organization?

n=57

InnerSource in Practice

Throughout the year in InnerSource Commons, we have discussed many InnerSource behaviors and practices. This section looked at which of these practices and behaviors were most in use at a project and team level. Many of the practices listed below will be familiar to those in the InnerSource Commons community, with documentation, findability, and modularity still areas where there may be room for improvement. It is also interesting to note that 15% of respondents do not accept inbound contributions to their InnerSource projects.

When thinking about InnerSource projects you have been involved with in the past year...

n=66

InnerSource in Organizations

InnerSource Trends

We asked two questions to assess levels of InnerSource activity and track momentum within our respondents' organizations. In terms of current activity, there was a spread across the answers, 40% of organizations reported being beyond early exploration, with their InnerSource practices either scaling or already well established. 36% describing their InnerSource practice as emerging or in pilot phase, while an additional 7% were just exploring the idea. 10% reported that InnerSource has neither leadership support or grassroots momentum.

Looking at trajectory, InnerSource appears broadly stable or advancing, with 34% sustaining and 32% scaling up. However, 14% reported a ramping down of support, which is an increase from last year, and perhaps correlates to the new top blocker (lack of time or resources).

Together, these results suggest that while InnerSource maturity varies, most organizations that responded have activity in place are maintaining or increasing their commitment.

How would you describe the current level of InnerSource activity at your organization?

n=59

How would you describe the current trajectory of InnerSource at your organization?

n=59

InnerSource Experience & Origins

There was a wide range of InnerSource experience among the respondents. 43% of respondents reported that InnerSource has been practiced in their organization for 5+ years and 32% have been practising InnerSource for less than 3 years. InnerSource may be initiated as a top-down or bottom-up initiative or, most often, a mix of both. Most organizations (47%) are currently scaling up their InnerSource practice.

How long ago with InnerSource first adopted in your organization?

How was InnerSource introduced to your organization?

Organization Motivation

We asked respondents to consider what motivated their organization to participate in InnerSource. When ranking motivation, code re-use came out on top (84%) and Development Speed came second (81%). Knowledge Sharing and Culture (e.g breaking down silos) came next at 79% and 77% respectively. The lowest ranking areas of org motivation were Open Source Readiness (40%) and Following Industry Trends (40%).

Which factors motivated your organization to participate in InnerSource?

n=53

InnerSource Progress & Measurement

When asked where respondents have seen “measurable progress” since adopting InnerSource, top-reported areas included Culture (e.g. breaking down silos) at 68% and Code Re-use (63%). Speed of Development and Software Quality scored 57% and 56% respectively. The lowest areas of reported progress included Following Industry Trends, Open Source Readiness, and People Benefits (36%, 35% and 33% respectively), correlating with their relatively lower scores in organizational motivation.

What areas have demonstrated measurable progress since adopting InnerSource?

n=53

Less than half of respondents shared how they measure InnerSource progress or success, and the top cited methods of measurement were Manual Tracking (42%) and surveys (38%). In terms of automated metrics, respondents referenced tracking use of an InnerSource Portal or Tool (28%). This suggests there is still a need for work on improving the identification and methods for measurement of InnerSource metrics.

How is progress or success of InnerSource measured at your organization?

n=53

InnerSource Resources

Most respondents report having foundational InnerSource elements in place, with 86% using shared code repositories and 60% providing InnerSource documentation, while more advanced support, such as discovery portals, training, metrics, and automation, is less consistently available. The results suggest that tooling is widely present at a basic level, but deeper enablement and operational support are still uneven.

What InnerSource tools and resources are available in your organization?

n=57

InnerSource Programs

There has been an increase in the number of respondents who have both formal (35%) and informal (29%) InnerSource Programs or ISPOs (InnerSource Program Offices). However, there was also an increase in those whose organizations reported that they had no plans to start an InnerSource Program (10% up from 4% in 2024). This could both recent progress in the creation of ISPOs and/or a redirection of priorities and investment from InnerSource Programs (towards AI initiatives, for example).

What best describes the status of InnerSource programs or initiatives at your organization?

n=52

InnerSource and Open Source

In 2025, we explored how organizations that practice InnerSource approach open source. Whereas there is no surprise that the majority (92%) reported using open source software, it is interesting to see the large proportion (79%) of organizations who practice InnerSource contributing to open source software projects. When taken with the fact that Open Source Readiness ranks relatively low as an organizational motivation for InnerSource, it perhaps indicates that organizations that contribute to open source projects are more likely to see opportunities for using open source practices internally to achieve a broad set of organizational benefits, other than just open source readiness.

Thinking about your organization’s approach to Open Source, select statements that are true...

n=53

InnerSource and GenAI

For the first year, we asked about respondents' experience of InnerSource in the context of the impact of GenAI in software development. Answers were split between the four areas we have heard discussed in InnerSource Commons working groups:

- Using InnerSource for sharing knowledge e.g. prompts
- Using InnerSource practices to build AI tools
- Integrating AI-generated code into InnerSource projects and workflows
- Using AI to automate InnerSource-related tasks (e.g. code review, documentation)

Those who responded typically were exploring more than one of these areas.

How is your organization currently experiencing the interplay between GenAI and InnerSource practices?

InnerSource Commons

This section of the survey aimed to find out how InnerSource Commons can better help respondents on their InnerSource journey. The most popular InnerSource enabling activities were reported to be discussions with other InnerSource practitioners (60%) and in-person events and meetups (56%). Top of the enabling resources included templates and best practice docs (50%) followed by InnerSource Patterns (48%), and the ISC events and community calls (44%).

What InnerSource enabling activities and resources have you engaged with and made use of? [Select all that apply]

About the Survey

Methodology

The State of InnerSource Survey 2025 was designed collaboratively by the InnerSource Commons community. Questions were reviewed and revised with community input.

The questionnaire was administered using Qualtrics, thanks to the support of the University of Galway, and was open for approximately 8 weeks in September and October 2025. The survey was promoted within the InnerSource Commons community (on Slack and on our Newsletter) and also across our social media channels. We had 119 respondents to the survey. Not every respondent answered every question. We removed respondents who only filled in their contact details but didn't answer any questions.

If you have any feedback on the survey or would like to get involved in future surveys, please reach out to info@innersourcecommons.org.

Demographics

Individual InnerSource Experience

Given that this survey is promoted to InnerSource Commons community members, it is perhaps not a surprise that the majority of respondents are experienced in InnerSource. More than half (59%) are involved in rolling out or scaling InnerSource in their organizations and have advised or coached other InnerSource practitioners.

Please select statements that describe your InnerSource experiences...

n=66

Gender

From our demographics, we can see an expected gender split with a majority of male respondents (80%). However, it is worth noting that the 18% female representation is more than [many estimates](#) of female contributors in the open source ecosystem.

Role

Respondents had a range of roles. 34% of respondents who specified their role identified as developers or software architects. 18% indicated they had a specialized InnerSource role, such as InnerSource Evangelist, InnerSource Program Office or Program Leader / Manager. Other roles included OSPO Manager (6%) engineering manager (6%), and senior executive (4%).

Select the role that most closely matches yours...

Work Experience

Respondents were experienced in their roles, with 64% having 15+ years of work experience.

Please state your work experience (in years)

Firmographics

Sector

As in previous years, respondents are working in a wide range of domains, with 55% coming from the technology industry. The category technology obviously comprises a wide range of companies offering many different types of services and products. As in previous surveys, respondents also work in the financial services domain, manufacturing, media and entertainment, healthcare & pharmaceuticals, and retail.

What is your organizational sector?

Org & Dev Org Size

45% of our respondents came from very large organizations (50,000+), and there was a wide spread of size of developer organizations.

How many software developers work in your organization?

How many people work in your organization?

Geographic Location

Respondents came from over 13 different countries. 55% came from Europe and 40% came from the Americas. Top countries were the United States and Germany.

Acknowledgments

Thanks to all who have helped us create and run this survey including: Sally Deering, Yuki Hattori, Daniel Izquierdo, and Eduardo Riberio.

Special thanks to our primary author:

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About InnerSource Commons

InnerSource Commons is the world's largest community of InnerSource practitioners. It is dedicated to creating and sharing knowledge about InnerSource, the use of open source best practices for software development within the confines of an organization. InnerSource helps organizations experience the benefits of using open source methods: reducing bottlenecks, increasing efficiencies, and creating happier developers.

Founded in 2015, the InnerSource Commons is now supporting and connecting over 4,000 individuals from over 1000 companies, academic institutions, and government agencies. The InnerSource Commons Foundation was incorporated on February 19th, 2020 and is a 501(c)(3) public charity.

Contact Information

You can reach us at info@innersourcecommons.org or visit the [InnerSource Commons Slack](#).

Learn More

Check out the InnerSource Commons website at www.innersourcecommons.org to find more resources such as our Learning Path, Patterns, Events, Research and more.